

A comparative and regional review of the exceptionalities, autism, and superior intelligence

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Abstract

This study elaborates a comparative review of the ASD, superior intelligence, and twice exceptional spectrum with their prevalence, difference, diagnostic, coexistence, and potential comorbidities focusing on a clinical and differential perspective. The dimensions of the multiple conditions and cognitive-behavioral disorders set challenges in and out academia, present with adverse diagnostic and converging processes that are ineffective with some clinical conditions that denote comorbidities and coexistence with other disorders. The lack of lineal and longitudinal studies in various domains of the exceptionalities, ASD, HIA or 2e, based on comorbidity factors and complex interdependent coexistence variables, elicit biometric gaps that impact accurate documentation, analysis, and assertive metric for a battery development that could offer effective identification, intervention, and program creation that benefit vulnerable population and their needs. ASD, HIA or giftedness, and 2e are often misdiagnosed encompassing a chain of neglectful procedures that lead to inadequate mechanisms, resulting in profound therapeutic deficit that could prevent the patient or learner from better opportunities in life and education quality. Additionally, the lack of alignment between behavioral science and education has unfavored observation, measurement, and effective services as these disciplines flourish asynchronously with a lack of conceptual and applied cohesion that allow a greater reach.

Keyword: autism spectrum disorder, twice-exceptional, high intellectual ability, giftedness, inclusive pedagogy, precision teaching

This comprehensive review explores historical perspectives and recent literature in the fields of special education, psychology, neuropsychology, and health with the objective of analyzing the broad spectrum of exceptionalities, with emphasis in autism, twice-exceptional, and superior intelligence. The present study aims to clarify the differences among these developmental disorders and emphasize characteristics and profiles that may be shared across clinical diagnostics. This analysis adopts a psycho-pedagogical approach, integrating multidisciplinary theoretical frameworks, and cross-dimensional factors that influence academic and pedagogical development in education and academic modeling.

Within the context of contemporary education, terms such as inclusion, pedagogy and precision teaching have acquired increasing prominence, particularly in relation to the exceptionalities and special education. However, the contextualization or clarity about the diverse conditions and their manifestations can deter the adequate approach within the classroom, requiring professional in education that hold professional certifications or specializations in special education or education psychology. Nowadays terms like neurodivergence and neuroatypical are words commonly used and coined to address individual with brain functions and abilities that set them apart. These terms refer to cognitive–intellectual disabilities and high intellectual abilities, including complex cases such as twice-exceptional, where outstanding talents coexist with cognitive–intellectual or behavioral disorders. These include neurodevelopmental conditions such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), learning disorders such as dyscalculia, dysgraphia, or dyslexia, and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), among others.

It is important to highlight that special education has evolved from a deficit-centered model toward an inclusive paradigm that recognizes neurodiversity as an educational value and critical element for curriculum development (García, 2009). This pedagogical transformation not only promotes more equitable practices adapted to the individual needs and each learner, but has also contributed to the advancement of teaching methodologies such as precision teaching. This method has been widely employed in the United States and Europe in the education of children and adolescents with ASD or neurodevelopmental disorders. Precision teaching seeks to provide appropriate stimuli to create optimal learning environments, applying behavioral metrics of response based on stimuli, eliciting behavioral patterns through stimulus–response principles that strengthen differentiated intervention and educational plans.

This practice centers on the cognitive and educational needs of the student, fostering assertive inclusion mechanisms, enabling learners of diverse abilities to coexist and develop in an integral form without neglecting their individual needs. Nevertheless, teachers must be equipped with the training and pedagogical skills to provide a comprehensive and effective education (Yarza de los Ríos, 2011).

The conceptual evolution of special education and exceptionalities has been profoundly shaped by contributions from disciplines such as psychology, particularly educational psychology, applied behavior analysis (ABA), and precision teaching grounded in principles of operant conditioning. Consequently, the advancement of a transformative and integrative educational model has not only enabled more humane and proactive perspectives, but has also contributed scientifically to the understanding of behavioral and cognitive models that promote academic inclusion (Valle, 2012). Within this theoretical–practical framework, psychopedagogy has expanded its scope, integrating the needs of students with high abilities and developmental disorders (Castillo-Bustos & Núñez-Naranjo, 2023).

Underscoring behavioral science’s theoretical and conceptual framework helps to understand the complexity and diversity of neurodivergence and ASD. Autism Spectrum Disorder is a neurodevelopmental disability caused by alterations in the brain function and neuroplasticity, characterized by the deficits in communication, social interaction, and behavioral patterns that may be restricted, generalized, or repetitive (Celis Alcalá & Ochoa Madrigal, 2022). ASD impacts not only behavioral domains but also affective, perceptual, and cognitive processes, leading individuals to perceive people, environments, and stimuli in differentiated, often erratic, and context-detached ways. As a result, ASD manifestations are highly heterogeneous, requiring constant revision of diagnostic criteria. Multidisciplinary frameworks including ABA, educational psychology, and psycho-pedagogy contextualizations can be effectively compressed to address the dimensionalities and primary factors in learners’ needs (León Pérez, 2016). The behavioral topography of ASD is indefinite and unquantifiable; however, some behavioral and cognitive variables are often inherent and coexist across various manifestations or degrees of autism. García & García (2022) emphasize the existence of multiple developmental trajectories in autism, underscoring the need for flexible clinical and educational perspectives to provide timely diagnosis and intervention. Therefore, psychopedagogical

intervention must be individualized, considering both the limitations and the potentialities of the student (Sánchez, 2000).

Curriculum design and instructional methodology are other essential components in traditional classroom contexts, but even more critical within the pedagogy of the exceptionality. It is important to establish a coherent understanding of the implications of exceptionalities and high intellectual abilities (HIA). The conceptual framework surrounding superior intelligence and exceptionalities has evolved, incorporating not only IQ metrics but also theories of multiple intelligences (MI) and neurodiversity, which have enabled a more integrative and assertive understanding of the high intellectual capacities and its behavioral traits involved. High intellectual ability implies functioning above the top 10% compared to individuals of the same age and similar natural capacity, developed either naturally or through structured psychobiological processes and composite stimuli (Nicolson & Fawcett, 2011). Consequently, results equal to or above the 95th percentile (WISC-IV IQ \geq 125), evaluating verbal comprehension, perceptual reasoning, working memory, and cognitive processing speed that also involve elements such as crystallized intelligence, representing intrinsic stimulus and experience, along fluid intelligence that are linked to adaptive skills. This includes conditioned and external stimuli with sensory information associated with synaptic processes that encompass various types of memory (Cervantes et al., 2022).

In the last decade, a high incidence of comorbidities amidst neurodevelopmental disorders and learning disabilities has been revealed, providing significant evidence regarding a largely overlooked school population, the twice-exceptional children and adolescents. These individuals demonstrate intellectual and attitudinal abilities superior to their chronological peers, yet are often masked by negligent diagnoses that fail to address their needs, falling into the context of learning disorders such as dyscalculia, dyslexia, dysgraphia, or neurodevelopmental conditions including ADHD or ASD. Clinically, twice-exceptional (2e) refers to the coexistence of HIA with a neurodevelopmental disorder such as ADHD, ASD, or specific learning disorders (SLD) like dyscalculia, dysgraphia, or dyslexia. These conditions present diagnostic and educational challenges, as the symptoms of one disorder may obscure the student's abilities, or vice versa (De la Caridad Fernández, 2019). Recent research has shown that individuals with 2e present complex cognitive and emotional profiles, requiring interventions based on cross-diagnostic approaches (Cervantes et al., 2022).

The study of 2e individuals has marked a milestone in curriculum development and the understanding of neurodivergence, being Europe and the United States pioneers in prognostic methods and therapeutic frameworks that employ complex, and integrative systems from multiple disciplines such as ABA, neuroscience, precision teaching, and educational sciences. In South America, Vélez-Calvo et al. (2023) identified a significant prevalence of this condition among schoolchildren, highlighting the need for inclusive educational policies and political normative structures for multidisciplinary diagnoses. This could direct educational science toward effective inclusivity offering a deeper understanding of neurodivergence, underscoring the need for adequately trained teachers with multidisciplinary qualifications.

Continuous and specialized training in inclusive pedagogical techniques and instructional strategies are essential for appropriate academic development, early detection, intervention planning, and successful school outcomes. Referring to the framework of pedagogical skill development and teacher training, twice-exceptional identification process remains uncertain and undetected, regardless of being a crucial facet of neurodivergence and superior intelligence. Indeed, Latin America development framework and novel policy articulation have been pivotal for the consolidation of inclusive education in the region. Conversely, from a critical perspective Azrak (2020) questions psychiatric discourses that medicalize neurodivergence and cognitive behavioral factors, emphasizing instead a psychosocial approach to these deficits with a more contextual and humanistic approach on neurodevelopmental disorders. Similarly, Intriago (2022) advocates for a multidisciplinary system, recognizing the complex dimensions of learning and human development.

Thereof, psychopedagogical and academic interventions must be flexible, collaborative, and student-centered, employing interdisciplinary nuances that not only enhance outcomes and benefit the individual, but also underscore the importance of such interventions in regular classrooms and within school integration programs (Torres & Briceño, 2020).

With respect to the conceptual and applied framework of 2e, prevalent cognitive and socio-affective variables are identified in individuals with HIA and attention disorders among the ASD spectrum. Unfortunately, in Latin America students that fall under any exceptionality often receive inefficient instructional models in terms of inclusive and pedagogical design (Conejero-Solar et al., 2018).

Early identification and intervention in cases of ASD, HIA, or ADHD portray significant challenges in modern education, encountering systemic obstacles and limited opportunities. Addressing 2e requires a high level of clinical and pedagogical expertise to enable conceptual, theoretical, and applied understanding of the spectrum, alongside the need of educational policies that guarantee mental health and educational quality. Twice-exceptional was first identified in 1970, conceptualized and studied by Elkind, who focused on a gifted student with SLD. Elkind introduced the construct that some individuals possess special needs alongside talents or abilities that remain academically unrecognized (Conejero-Solar et al., 2018).

Students classified as 2e typically fall under three prevalent scenarios: first, when HIA is masked by a learning disorder; second, when high abilities compensate for cognitive or behavioral development through intrinsic self-regulation strategies, thereby concealing academic difficulties or cognitive disabilities; and third, when HIA and learning disorders interact reciprocally, minimizing one another without exclusion, thus obscuring salient traits of both variables and complicating detection and treatment (Conejero-Solar et al., 2018). Regardless of these three potential scenarios, detection, treatment, and behavioral modification require multiple diagnostic batteries and complex data-collection systems involving stakeholders like families, classmates, teachers, and close individuals who interact with the student. There is a notable lack of data about the prevalence of 2e in Latin American research, unveiling a significant gap in studies on 2e and HIA. This portrays an inaccurate data in research and constitute major challenges in the field of special education, impacting the applicability of the modern conception of exceptionalities, HIA, and ASD.

On the other hand, classical concepts often homogenize diagnostic profiles, stereotyping behavioral and biometric characteristics of children and adolescents, relying on orthodox models of IQ or high academic performance. In pedagogy and academic development, instructors often rely on labels and stereotypes, indirectly fostering hostile environments. Nevertheless, there is a tendency among experienced mental health professionals and educators to associate inappropriate behavior, irregular conduct patterns, social difficulties, and non-neurotypical verbal behavior with HIA. It is crucial to emphasize that behavioral variations and disorders are undefined and indeterminate; they do not follow a specific pattern and may not be linked to a salient trait or diagnose. To differentiate HIA, one salient trait is the rapid logical processing and metacognitive capacity, integrating prior knowledge into complex data networks that enable

multiple solutions in a record time. HIA individuals also demonstrate emotional decoupling, which is the ability to detach internal stimuli, and to make assertive - functional decisions.

Within the framework of pedagogical development and behavioral studies in the classroom, Precision Teaching (PT) offers an opportunity to scientifically evaluate instructional and curricular tools, focusing on the effectiveness of pedagogical practices, measurement of learning, and responsive patterns to instructional delivery (Evan et al., 2021). PT is rooted in informed instructional decision-making, originated at Harvard in the 1950s under Ogden Lindsley and with the supervision of Skinner. Although this systemic method has been widely used to improve instructional tactics, behavioral repertoires, and adaptive curricular strategies, it is also a powerful tool applicable beyond ASD. Instructional decisions and metrics using PT can support students with learning disorders and individuals with HIA that encounter serious challenges. PT enables the development of objectives and cognitive-behavioral growth patterns based on stimulus-response, environment, and operant conditioning, creating new behavioral or corrective opportunities that benefit mental and emotional health, reinforcing affective and cognitive foundations toward prosperous and autonomous development.

Methods

This study employs a systematic literature review of empirical studies on executive functions (EF), comorbidity, coexistence, and theoretical-conceptual frameworks within the disciplines of psychopedagogy, psychology, and education. In addition, through historical and literary metrics, analyzing regional and international policies to address high intellectual abilities, twice-exceptional, Autism Spectrum Disorder, and other conditions that affect learning development and neurodivergence. The study proposes a differential perspective on prognosis amid clinical profiles that are often misinterpreted, leading to deficiencies in academic support, and coping therapies. The analyzed and coded documents are bounded by empirical, experimental, quantitative, and qualitative research in multiple languages, enabling the construction of a macro-functional framework that identifies global shortcomings in the study of the exceptionalities, ASD, HIA, and 2e.

The articles research was conducted through direct access to several educational institutions in LATAM and in the United States, referencing high-impact scientific journals in education, psychopedagogy, and psychology with a data extraction that was organized into a

literary matrix that examined references, type of study, discipline, focus, findings, results, and conclusions, correlating these with psychosocial, educational, and policy implications for inclusion. This allows an integrative documentation coding, reviewing highly relevant content, theoretical and conceptual frameworks of HIA, ASD, 2e, and other neurodevelopmental disorders associated with these diagnoses.

Results

The systematic analysis yields five qualitative results, ensuring: 1. Prevalence of misdiagnosis in 2e conditions, 2. Comorbidities as well as coexistence among different ASD and 2e conditions, 3. Differentiated and revealing executive functions across clinical profiles, 4. Need for training in pedagogical skills and identification, and finally, 5. Improvement of social policies that allow effective identification, diagnosis, and treatment for assertive academic inclusion. The academic scenario and diversification have evolved, and likewise, the needs within the framework of effective and timely pedagogy, requiring for a more humanistic yet technical approach that facilitates multidisciplinary axes safeguarding the proper development of students, whether they are children, adolescents, or adults.

The need for educational support in the classroom has grown, also conveying variables of social needs based on psychology, psycho-pedagogy, and behavioral sciences, capable of providing attention to special educational needs, but also with competent and empathetic professionals that are able to address exceptionalities with their differentiated spectrum under the educator role (Espinoza-Vásquez, 2019).

Different studies conclude with significant evidence regarding misdiagnosis within the 2e spectrum, requiring a behavioral science approach that emphasize theoretical and experimental basis, establishing functionality and objectives according to the behavior's topography aligned within sociocultural and behavioral patterns. This establishes the need for the development of a psycho-pedagogical matrix in convergence with behavioral sciences, involving the understanding of learning across dimensions and manifestations of individual needs that encompass the intervention and its design merging psychosocial, occupational, and clinical aspects. The learning process entails complex heuristic processes that have been approached from various perspectives and forms, but with prominent barriers for learners and their neurodevelopment.

Neuro-atypical individuals and those with neurodevelopmental disorders often present high prevalence of comorbidities, also manifesting the coexistence of one or more learning or

behavioral disorders, representing profound challenges in the individual's life inside and outside the academia. Assuming that cognitive, sensory, and motor processes are indispensable for reading, writing, and vocalization, potential comorbidity and transferability amid different learning disorders are presumed (Dohla & Heim, 2016). These cognitive or sensory deficiencies, such as dyslexia, impacted on the Wernicke's area, which is specialized brain area that process language, sound identification, words, and their relationships. This SLD is permanent causing lifelong challenges in reading, writing, and spelling,

It should be noted that there is a prominent prevalence of dysgraphia and dyslexia with manifestations of composite comorbidities in individuals with ASD, with similarities in comorbidities in learning disorders in children with ADD and ADHD (David, 2025). Both dysgraphia and dyslexia also appear prevalent in individuals with HIA, who demonstrate exceptional abilities in one or more domains while simultaneously presenting focalized learning or attention difficulties, clinically defined as 2e. Unfortunately, these learning and behavioral disorders are difficult to detect, making subsequent studies a challenge that requires multidisciplinary approaches and differential diagnostic batteries. Additionally, although these disorders have no cure, the emotional impact of a formal diagnosis must be considered, as it allows the individual to achieve a more realistic self-awareness, producing positive and attuned effects in their daily life (David, 2025).

Behavioral disorders and neurodivergence have denoted functional correlations, as there is a relationship between learning disorders, auditory skills, and visual deficits that are oriented toward spatial attention. Therefore, a distortion in the development and cohesion of phonological and orthographic skills would be an indirect and consequent representation of attention and spatial deficits that diminish the individual's ability to learn, read, or focus. Studies in human behavior and neuroscience distinguish a latent relationship between attention deficit or ADHD and neurodevelopmental and learning disorders such as dysgraphia, dyslexia, or dyscalculia. Individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders present marked prevalence in dysgraphia, which represents a challenge in acquiring writing, comprehension, and reading skills; likewise, dyslexia is prevalent in individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders (Dohla & Heim, 2016).

Scientifically, the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2014) distinguishes and classifies writing and reading disorders within the categories of *SLD with impairment in reading [315.00 (F81.00)]* and *SLD with impairment in mathematics [315.2 (F81.81)]*. It is important to

mention that within these macro classifications, there are two subgroups: specific disorder with impairment in reading, which may vary, impacting effective reading, rate and fluency, or reading comprehension; and specific disorder with impairment in written expression, divided into problems such as spelling, grammar, punctuation, clarity, or organization of written expressions (Dohla & Heim, 2016). Another prevalent developmental learning disorder is dyscalculia, although this disorder is not separately classified in the DSM-5, instead is referenced as a combined disorder in mathematics, reading, and writing.

Studies on the autistic spectrum and learning disorders such as dysgraphia, dyslexia, or dyscalculia have shown diagnostic inaccuracy between HIA and ADHD, overlapping behavioral and executive characteristics that require differential diagnosis and multidisciplinary examinations (Cervantes et al., 2022). Latest neuroscience studies confirm some comorbidities in neurodevelopmental and learning disorders. Nicolson and Fawcett (2011) describe considerable overlap between mental disorders and neurodevelopmental disorders, presenting high comorbidity rates ranging from 25% to 40%, connecting inclusive criteria within ASD, dyspraxia, and neural activity abnormalities. Highlighting neural activities involving the cortico-cerebellar area, being considered critical for the neural and integrative learning systems. Any abnormality in this brain area translates into generative factors for potential comorbidities and disabilities, including paroxysmal events that impact declarative and procedural memory, allowing the individual to construct facts and knowledge, as well as access and differentiate information. This indicates that neural circuits affecting declarative and procedural memory are critically connected to learning in early life stages and development, being determinants in neurodevelopment, cognitive capacity, or impairment.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics

Group	Cognitive profile	Executive function	Academic pattern	Diagnostic notes
ASD	Strengths in systematization, perceptual reasoning, differences in social cognition	Impact planning, observation & variability	Atypical and irregular academic development; impact on social participation and pragmatism	DSM-5 diagnostic guide, batteries assessing language, social domains, and adaptive skills

HIA	High reasoning and metacognition. Enhanced creativity, mastery in specific domains (language, art, music, communication)	EF with strong capacity, powerful memory, atypical inhibition and cognitive control	Prevalence of academic achievement; possible borderline personality traits due to asynchrony or disinterest	Identification often inefficient and non-traditional with risks of overlooking cross-diagnoses of learning or behavioral disorders
2e (HIA + ASD/ADHD/SLD)	Asynchronous with high reasoning abilities but deficits in learning or behavioral response	High-performing EF coexisting with vulnerabilities in inhibition and memory; abilities mask cognitive or behavioral weaknesses	Excels in certain academic areas but faces severe challenges in others	Requires integrative methods with diverse diagnostic batteries to minimize risks of under-identification or misdiagnosis

In this complex scenario, academic preparation and professional background are essential to create a safe learning environment that promote consistent skills and scope. Professionals trained in psycho-pedagogy or education differs in approach compared to educational psychologists, making these educators operate in parallel, asynchronous, and mostly misaligned ways (Vergara-Rodríguez et al., 2025). The salient comorbidity and coexistence in learning and behavioral disorders are not only challenges in school-age populations, but their co-occurrence makes identification, diagnosis, and intervention complex and limited, affecting academic performance and timely development of children or adolescents (Han, 2025).

The limitation in the identification of co-occurrences and comorbidities represents a high educational and emotional impact. These disorders, in many cases, have genetic associations linked to structural differences in the left angular gyrus or hypo-activation of brain regions responsible for language, among other complex neural processes, requiring triangulated research to elucidate new answers and better understanding of the problem (Han, 2025).

Environmental and genetic factors, as well as regional educational policies are key in academic policies, particularly in early intervention programs, academic support plans, curricular

modification, and multidisciplinary frameworks that promote systemic synergy in resource organization and distribution for student well-being that can satisfy cultural diversity, neurodiversity, and academic needs (Herrera et al., 2016). It is clear that the education and scope in the classroom that could effectively address neurodivergent individuals' needs not only demand skills but also the development of specific disciplines that require a strong focus on research that serve for innovative pedagogical strategies.

The importance of epistemological and interdisciplinary studies is critical as this could help redefining instructional methodologies and knowledge acquisition processes by using theoretical and conceptual frameworks that best align with the diverse population and their needs. Primarily, this involves shifting special and exceptional education from a set of services and support to a dynamic and cohesive curricular framework into a permanent classroom integration with qualified professionals with multidisciplinary skills that serve student needs (Meléndez-Rodríguez, 2020). Additionally, in the process of research and professional development, educational psychology and psycho-pedagogy must achieve a cohesive development, enriching interdisciplinary skills with methodology and scientific contributions (Valdivieso, 2009).

Discussion

Studies over the past decades have not deepened nor made an effective differentiation between the broad spectrum of neurodivergent conditions and atypical neural functioning. This indicates the need for longitudinal studies that provide reliable and enriching information on the development and improvement of patients who have a condition that, although treatable and attenuated with therapy, remains with a diagnosis that has an impact for the rest of their life.

The spectrum of the exceptionalities, high intellectual abilities, and their awareness in educational context are frequently rendered invisible in traditional systems. HIA not only implies a high intellectual quotient but also creative, motivational, communicative, or socio-emotional skills that misalign with age or expected skills (Piedrahita, 2023). These skills or abilities are evident in individuals who demonstrate superior capacity or talent that exceeds acquired learning, training, or crystallized and fluid intelligence, differing from their chronological age.

Children with high intellectual abilities possess atypical behavior patterns, advanced vocabulary, deep curiosity about their environment, and elevated control of executive functions, which allow them to perform analyses, metacognitive processes, and meta-structured problem-

solving, reaching a vast probability of solutions in record time. These individuals with HIA may also present ASD manifestations or traits, showing comorbidities in other dimensions, both behavioral and psycho-emotional.

A gifted child may face social challenges such as anhedonia, social isolation, or oppositional disorders. These behavioral–emotional alterations in individuals with HIA derive from imbalances in stimulus–response dynamics, as they require more meaningful stimulation focused on their interests or high abilities. Traditional education and family environments are often inefficient in meeting their intellectual potential, which transforms into different responses modeled according to immediate extrinsic stimuli and expository behavioral patterns.

Indeed, early identification and appropriate intervention are essential to avoid academic underperformance and maladaptive behaviors (Álvarez Cárdenas et al., 2019). Academic and psychological intervention must be personalized, considering the individual’s unique variables and metrics, their environment, stimuli, and potentialities to produce an accurate diagnosis and planning (Parra, 2006). The approach of educational psychology and ABA toward a comprehensive treatments reveals the need to adopt an interdisciplinary approach in the area of special education and exceptionalities as neuroplasticity may be discerned more adequately, in contrast to a psycho-pedagogical approach that may limit the understanding of behaviors, affective dimensions, and the variety of clinical profiles in this population.

Intellectual motivational and intervention delve across a variety of processes in which are critical a multidisciplinary knowledge with a focus on behavioral sciences, behavioral modification, cognitive, and affective systems that converge in complex semantics around the stimulus–response that is provided by the environment, and those variables that can be manipulated to favor the individual’s wellbeing. The professional practice in the education community accentuates learning issues primarily as neuropsychological disorders derived from sociocultural and economic deficiencies, leaving aside other diagnostic possibilities that could improve policy-making in school programs, educational management policies, and evaluation criteria that are more realistic with the learners’ condition and cognitive–behavioral conditions (Vergara-Rodríguez et al., 2025).

Conclusions

Research, measurement, intervention, and academic inclusion programs have emerged as central themes in recent decades, making clear the need for conceptual and educational

frameworks with broad approaches on the spectrum of neurodiversity and exceptionalities. Pioneering regions in intervention and coping designs, such as the United States and Europe, have not only enabled the evolution of therapeutic and diagnostic systems for many clinical and pedagogical conditions, but have also facilitated the development of cognitive-behavioral tools that foresee significant improvements in the quality of life of individuals with special needs. These advances contribute to new expectations in academic development within an inclusive architecture that leads them to learn and grow according to their specific abilities or needs with a more humane and equitable perspective.

The emphatic progress of human understanding of behavioral, cognitive, and stimulus patterns contributes to the creation of therapeutic tools, both clinical and psycho-pedagogical. ABA, stimulus-response, precision teaching, and conditioning serve as the foundations for curricular or adaptive modifications that strengthen academic architecture toward effective and assertive knowledge delivery. This promotes inclusion, appropriate management, and social policies that make visible the real needs of a neurodivergent population with unique patterns in knowledge acquisition and behavior.

It should be emphasized that an extensive list of studies supports the understanding and development of cognitive-behavioral techniques; however, not all delve into the observation and measurement of conditions, comorbidities, and coexistence of disorders. This makes evident the primary need for more studies on 2e with the marked coexistence of cognitive-behavioral disorders in individuals diagnosed with ASD, and HIA. The proper development of individuals with unique abilities depends on assertive management and diagnosis, fostering autonomy, adequate environment, safety, and motivation that render proper stimulus-response toward growth at their own pace in a secure manner with effective and affective structures that ensure new opportunities and a better quality of life.

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